

Polarographic Behaviour of Chromium(VI) at the Dropping Mercury Electrode

P. C. JAIN* & S. P. BANERJEE

Department of Chemistry, Saugar University, Saugar

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Kolthoff and Lingane¹ have observed the polarographic reduction of chromate ions in sodium hydroxide. A single well defined wave was obtained with a half-wave potential of -0.85 volts. Urone *et al.*² have described a polarographic method for the determination of chromium in dusts and mists. Issa *et al.*³ have studied the polarographic behaviours of chromate and dichromate ions within the limits $0.2-2.0$ mM. Polarographic behaviours of chromium(VI) have been studied by several workers using different electrolytes⁴⁻⁸. The present work deals with the study of the polarographic reductions of chromate, molybdate, and tungstate ions using potassium chloride-phosphoric acid supporting electrolyte. Whereas the Mo(VI) and W(VI) ions are reduced successively to the penta- and tri-valent states, Cr(VI) is not reduced reversibly. Use of gelatin as maxima suppressor in the case of CrO_4^{2-} results in the suppression of its polarographic wave in $0.1M$ sodium hydroxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of Analar quality. Freshly prepared gelatin (0.01%) was used as maxima suppressor. Purified hydrogen was passed through each solution to remove dissolved oxygen. Double distilled water was used in preparing the solutions. Doubly distilled mercury was used for DME. Polarograms were obtained using a pen-recording polarograph, PO₄ Radiometer Polariter. A Beckmann pH-meter with a combined glass-calomel electrode was used for measuring pH. All the operations were carried out at room temperature (24.8°). The drop-time (3.0 seconds per drop), sensitivity ($50 \mu\text{A}$), damping⁷, and chart speed (2 cms per minute) were kept constant. These operational conditions are for Cr(VI) only. The experimental conditions for Mo(VI) have been included in a separate communication⁹.

Fig. 1

* Present Address: Dept. of Chemistry, C.M.D. Post-Graduate College, Bilaspur (M.P.).

DISCUSSION

Figures 1A, B, C, D and 2A, B, C exhibit the polarograms obtained with Mo (VI) and Cr (VI) ions respectively, in 1M potassium chloride and $7.5 \times 10^{-3}M$ phosphoric acid. In the case of Mo (VI) its reduction to +5 and then to +3 molybdenum is clearly shown by two clear waves with halfwave potentials of -0.58 volts and -0.90 volts respectively. Figure 2 on the other hand shows that Cr (VI) is not reduced reversibly. Figure 3 shows the polarograms of Cr (VI) in 0.1M sodium hydroxide. The wave begins at -0.7 volts and

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

the half-wave potential is observed to be -0.90 volts. This value is independent of the Cr (VI) ion concentration. The pH of the solutions remains constant at 12.0. The electrode reaction is reversible and proceeds, according to Kolthoff and Lingane (*loc. cit.*), as follows showing transfer of three electrons :

Addition of a 0.01% solution of gelatin suppresses almost totally the wave due to the Cr (VI) ions. This study of the behaviour of Cr (VI), Mo (VI), and W(VI) establishes certain interesting facts. While Cr (VI) is reduced quantitatively to +3 state in the alkaline medium without gelatin being added, Mo (VI) and W (VI) are reduced first to +5 and then to +3 states only in the acid medium. Their polarographic reduction is not possible in the alkaline medium¹⁰. By the careful selection of medium and potential range, quantitative separation of Cr (VI) is possible from Mo (VI) and W (VI).

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